

Off-Hull Radio Frequency Emissions from Below-Deck Spaces in Ships

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Abstract — Measurement results and model analyses are presented for off-hull RF emissions caused by intentional transmitters radiating at 2.4 GHz and 5.8 GHz in enclosed, reflective spaces typically found within ships and aircraft. These transmissions can originate from shipboard wireless local area networks, radio frequency identification (RFID) tags and readers, handheld radios, and telemetry sources. Reverberant below-deck spaces with direct access to open air through windows and hatches exhibit surprisingly large off-hull signals detectable at substantial distances from the ship or aircraft. This situation occurs for total radiated power from the (multiple) transmitters at levels as low as 10 – 25 mW inside the below-deck space.

Keywords—Radiated emissions; electromagnetic environment

I. INTRODUCTION

The electromagnetic environment (EME) in electrically large, enclosed, reflective spaces, such as found in ships and aircraft, often exhibits features of a complex reverberant cavity [1,2]. The full diffuse, or multi-path, nature of the field in these cavities has significant bearing on radio frequency (RF) energy propagation between coupled spaces and RF energy emission from the ship or aircraft to the external environment. This work investigates the off-hull leakage, or emissions control (EMCON), of transmissions from wireless network access points in below-deck spaces. Emissions testing is conducted from complex cavity spaces with various apertures (clear openings, windows) and hatch structures with direct access to the ship exterior. Figure 1 shows an EMCON test at a distance from a ship. These off-hull RF emissions have been assessed for several classes of surface ships, as well as for pier-side submarines and fighter aircraft.

Section II describes in detail the emissions test from a reverberant shipboard space. Results of the measured data are provided in Section III, and are compared with the predictions of a simple model. The conclusion is presented in Section IV.

Figure 1. Measurement of off-hull RF emissions from surface ship

II. EMISSIONS TEST

This paper reports continuous wave (CW) emissions at 2.4 GHz and 5.8 GHz measured from the Bridge of an aircraft carrier, shown in Fig. 2. Data collection used two observation points: (1) a car parking structure on the shore 447 meters directly in front of the ship, approximately 20 meters in elevation and (2) an 08-level catwalk on an adjacent aircraft carrier, at approximately the same elevation and 240 meters to the starboard side.

The electromagnetic environment of the Bridge space does exhibit reflective cavity effects due to multiple scattering paths off walls, windows, equipment, cabling and consoles in the space. Chaotic changes in the standing-wave field pattern are caused by perturbations in cavity boundary conditions, such as occur from movement of personnel, equipment, and hatches. In this environment, the familiar direct line-of-sight space-loss propagation relationship, with received power set deterministically by antenna separation and gain, does not hold. Instead, it is replaced by a diffuse-field (multi-path propagation) insertion loss [3]. Figure 3 depicts multi-path illumination of a Bridge window. The RF energy transmitted

Figure 2. RF radiated emissions from the ship Bridge (08 level)

into the Bridge space is “stirred” in order to assess the statistical nature of the multi-path effect. One means to accomplish this is to physically stir the energy within a space using an electrically conductive rotating tuner assembly. Source stirring is another technique, where the transmit antenna is physically moved (carried) throughout the space. Reverberation chamber tests have demonstrated that the two stirring techniques are statistically equivalent, and both have been used in shipboard tests [4]. With sufficient number of modes excited in a complex cavity, the central limit theorem states that the vector field components are normally distributed with zero mean and equal standard deviation [5]. Hence, as the RF energy is stirred, the sampled received power of a linearly polarized antenna in the space should follow a chi-squared distribution with two degrees of freedom (χ_2^2). Demonstration of a χ_2^2 power distribution in a space is a good indicator of its reverberant nature, and allows us to utilize statistical inference to predict such things as maximum field values within specified levels of confidence.

Insertion loss measurements in the Bridge space are obtained using a “walk-around” method for reverberant environments [4]. For this test, the transmit (Tx) antenna is mounted at one end of a 1-m pole, with the receive (Rx) antenna mounted cross polarized and pointed in the opposite direction at the other end of the pole. The moving Tx antenna injects 1mW (0dBm) of power into the space. The moving Rx antenna samples power throughout the volume in maximum-hold mode while the frequency of the

Figure 3. Multi-path propagation in Bridge cavity

transmitting tracking generator sweeps slowly (2 sec) from 400MHz to 6GHz and the operator walks casually around the space. Both transmit and receive antennas are continuously manipulated to achieve different aspect angles and polarizations as they move throughout the space. A “run” is complete when the max-hold trace on the spectrum analyzer has stabilized during the walk-around. For statistical analysis, 12 separate runs through the Bridge are executed.

Insertion loss data shown in this paper represent power loss (in dB) between the maximum received power from the Rx antenna and the input power into the Tx antenna. Insertion loss characterization of the space provides information on the expected average and maximum power density in the stirred volume for a given total radiated power into that space. At 2.4 GHz and 5.8 GHz, the over-moded, reflective Bridge space does support complex cavity field patterns that follow the expected statistical properties. Consequently, a portion of the stirred power density in the volume is “incident” on an effective cross-section of the Bridge windows, leading to radiated emissions to open air. This has been demonstrated using computational electromagnetic ray-casting simulations [6], and is representative of the actual conditions in the Bridge with an operating wireless network access point transmitting into the space.

Off-hull measurements of radiated emissions utilize a Tx antenna moving randomly throughout the Bridge space to achieve effective source stirring. The Tx antenna is never pointed directly through the window at the distant Rx antenna which is sighted at the Bridge from several off-ship locations with both vertical and horizontal polarizations. The Tx antenna injects 100mW (20dBm) CW power at 2.4 GHz and 5.8 GHz into the volume.

III. TEST RESULTS

A. Cavity Insertion Loss Characterization

In processing the raw data from the walk-around measurement technique in the ship's Bridge, a thru calibration corrects for tracking generator output power variation, cable attenuation, and 3-dB attenuator pad used for matching at the Tx antenna. Antenna correction factors, based on measured differences in insertion loss of the ETS Lindgren 3117 antennas and standard log-periodic antennas located in the NSWCCD Reverberation Chamber, are applied to both transmit and receive antennas at frequencies below 1 GHz. Figure 4 shows measured Max-Hold received power data that have been averaged over the twelve walk-around runs. The average is a frequency-dependent value that represents space insertion loss. The range of measurement uncertainty is indicated by the maximum and minimum extents, and is less than ± 3 dB.

Bridge insertion loss (which is a measure of the resonant quality factor Q_{cavity}) is found to be similar to other comparable below-deck spaces measured aboard many ships. The quality factor Q_{cavity} includes power dissipation (aperture loss) due to the presence of the Bridge windows.

Figure 4. Measured insertion loss in the ship Bridge

A cavity calibration factor (CCF), or normalized electric field in $\text{V/m}/\sqrt{\text{W}}$ [7], characterizes the electromagnetic environment in the space.

$$CCF \equiv \text{Normalized } E_{\text{Max}} = \frac{E_{\text{Max}}}{\sqrt{P_{\text{input}}}} = \frac{8\pi}{\lambda} \sqrt{\frac{5 \cdot IL}{\eta_{rx}}} \quad (1)$$

where insertion loss (IL) is the quotient of measured maximum power to total input power emitted into the space,

$$I.L. \equiv \frac{\langle P_{\text{Max,rec}} \rangle_{\text{run.}}}{P_{\text{input}}} \quad (2)$$

and η_{rx} is receive antenna efficiency. Once the cavity calibration factor has been determined for a space, the maximum electric field component amplitude in that space can be predicted. For source-victim separations greater than a critical distance governed by free-space loss and antenna directivity, the maximum electric field at the victim will be dominated by the diffuse (multi-path) field, and can be estimated by,

$$E_{\text{max}} \equiv CCF \sqrt{P_{\text{input}}} \quad (3)$$

where P_{input} is total power radiated into the space at the given frequency. P_{input} is the summation of radiated power from each source in case of multiple emitters at a given frequency. The CCF values at the wireless frequencies 2.4 GHz and 5.8 GHz are $11 \text{ V/m}/\sqrt{\text{W}}$ and $7 \text{ V/m}/\sqrt{\text{W}}$, respectively. From measurements in over 100 below-deck spaces in ships, values of CCF are found in the 5-20 $\text{V/m}/\sqrt{\text{W}}$ range. The expected maximum electric field environment at 2.4 GHz is estimated from equation (3) and is plotted in Fig. 5 compared to the below-deck limit established in MIL-STD-461F [8].

Figure 5. Electromagnetic environment in ship Bridge for total power radiated into the space

B. Off-Hull Radiated Emissions

Knowledge of the average power density in the Bridge enables prediction of power leaked through windows for EMCON analysis using a simple model. Figure 3 depicts power leakage from a below-deck cavity space with aperture coupling to the exterior, based on the assumption that the window aperture is illuminated by a field profile with random variable amplitude and phase. Hence, statistically, there is no 'focusing' or array effect of the aperture in the far field (i.e., unity aperture antenna gain), and the average power density P_d incident on the aperture

establishes an effective isotropic radiated power P_{leak} emitted from the window [9],

$$P_{leak} = \frac{1}{2} P_d \langle \sigma_{ap} \rangle \quad (4)$$

For an electrically-large aperture of arbitrary shape with area A , the geometrical optics approximation is valid, and the effective transmission cross section $\langle \sigma_{ap} \rangle$ averaged over a 2π -steradian solid angle is given by

$$\langle \sigma_{ap} \rangle \cong \frac{1}{2} A T_{eff} \quad (5)$$

where the transmittivity T_{eff} is the intensity transmission coefficient for the window averaged over $0-\pi/2$ radian incident angles. Bridge window transmittivity was measured independently to be -8 dB and -6 dB at 2.4 GHz and 5.8 GHz, respectively. Average power density P_d in (4) can be approximated from the measured insertion loss IL in the space (2) as

$$P_d = \frac{8\pi}{\eta_{rx}\eta_{tx}\lambda^2} \frac{IL}{\xi} P_{tx} \quad (6)$$

where ξ is the statistical max-to-mean power ratio in the cavity and P_{tx} is the total power transmitted into the cavity at the given frequency. Combining (4) – (6) yields

$$\frac{P_{leak}}{P_{tx}} = \frac{Q_{cavity}}{Q_{aperture}} \quad (7)$$

where

$$Q_{cavity} = \frac{16\pi^2 Vol}{\eta_{rx}\eta_{tx}\lambda^3} \frac{IL}{\xi} \quad (8)$$

$$Q_{aperture} = \frac{8\pi Vol}{\lambda A} \frac{1}{T_{eff}} \quad (9)$$

P_{leak} in (7) can be treated as effective isotropic radiation from the window aperture in the far field under assumption of a well-stirred space. Although the volume of the space enters the expressions in (8) and (9) for the quality factors Q of both the cavity and the aperture, the leaked power P_{leak} in (7) is independent of volume. This is fortunate, because typically the volume of below-deck spaces is not easily measured, and in some cases, not well defined. The leaked power does depend strongly on the insertion loss characteristics of the complex cavity through surface area, wall material effective conductivity, frequency, loading, stirring effectiveness, etc.

Figures 6 and 7 show measured maximum receive power data, converted to power density incident on the receive

ETS Lindgren 3117 horn antenna using calibration data for antenna gain. Due to the very large number of samples acquired during the Max-Hold measurement as the Bridge space energy is stirred, the statistical uncertainty in the measurements are on order ± 1 dB. In Table I, the measured power density values at the two observation locations are compared with model results calculated from the effective isotropic radiated power predicted in (7) and the Friis free-space propagation equation. An average 3-dB enhancement due to a single ground bounce is assumed in the model calculation. Other physical values used in the model are shown in the calculation spreadsheet in Table II.

Figure 6. Measured maximum received power at 447 m at 2.445 GHz

Figure 7. Measured maximum received power at 240 m at 5.845 GHz

TABLE I.
Comparison of Measured and Calculated Off-Hull RF Emissions

Distance/ Direction	2.4 GHz		5.8 GHz	
	P _{density, measured} dB mW/m ²	P _{density, calculated} dB mW/m ²	P _{density, measured} dB mW/m ²	P _{density, calculated} dB mW/m ²
240 m / Starboard	-40.3	-41.2	-46.3	-44.5
447 m / Forward	-44.8	-46.6	-50.6	-49.9

TABLE II.
Model Calculation for Off-Hull RF Emission from Bridge at 447 m at 5.845 GHz

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Values for radiated power density can be extrapolated out to a distance of one nautical mile (1 NM) as stipulated in MIL-STD-464A using the Friis equation [10]

$$P_{\text{density}}(1 \text{ NM}) = P_{\text{density}}(d \text{ meters}) - 20 \log(1852/d) \quad (10)$$

MIL-STD-464A specifies a maximum allowed EMCON power density of -110 dBmW/m² at a distance of 1 NM. Using the measurement at 5.8 GHz at 447 m forward of the

Bridge, the extrapolated EMCON power density at 1 NM is -63 dBmW/m². Since operational wireless access points transmit digitally modulated signals; EMCON results should be adjusted to lower power density values to take into account the power spectral density difference between CW and 802.11b/g modulated signals. From spectrum analyzer measurements of 802.11b/g modulation schemes, an allowance of approximately 12 dB can be taken for this adjustment. Furthermore, wireless transmitters are typically operated at total radiated power levels less than the 100 mW

used in these tests. A reduction of 6 dB in total radiated power to 25 mW is common. Nevertheless, it is clear that the EMCON specification is exceeded by a margin on the order of 25 – 30 dB. Hence, further consideration is warranted for off-hull RF emissions as a result of wireless network transmissions from reverberant below-deck spaces with aperture coupling to the outside environment.

IV. CONCLUSION

With the proliferation of wireless technologies currently being deployed in a wide variety of confined, reflective spaces, it is important to understand the radio frequency (RF) propagation through multiply-connected spaces for the purpose of evaluating access point coverage or shielding effectiveness of structures and enclosures. Such coupled-cavity spaces can be found in below-deck compartments and passageways in ships, ammunition containers in bunkers, aircraft cabins and bays, and buildings such as hangars and pre-fabricated metal storage facilities. In assessing the potential impact associated with the use of intentional RF emitters in coupled reverberant spaces, we must address the cumulative build-up and exchange of electromagnetic energy in these spaces. The eventual leakage of this energy to the external environment through apertures and seams of windows and hatches is of particular concern as it constitutes a real security threat.

This investigation provides test results and model analyses of measurements of off-hull RF emissions from intentional transmitters inside ship spaces. These transmissions can originate from shipboard wireless local area networks, radio frequency identification (RFID) tags and readers, handheld radios, and telemetry sources. It is found that surprisingly large off-hull signals are detectable and intelligible at substantial distances from the ship. This situation occurs for total radiated power from the (multiple) transmitters at levels as low as 10 – 25 mW inside the below-deck space. EMCON tests for pier-side submarines, fighter aircraft, and other surface ships have exhibited similar results. Efforts are underway to develop a probability of effect analysis that will aid E³ engineers in assessing and mitigating risk factors associated with these emissions.

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